

Fig S7. Parameter study with varying regularization parameter λ_{reg} during polarized cell motility. For each cell track the same protrusion component is underlying (top left). The center of mass trajectory (colored lines) as well as the covered area of each cell track (gray area) are displayed (top right). Based on different regularization schemes, different kymographs are computed: Local motion (left column), the APCSF component (middle column), and the AAF component (right column). Regions of interest are displayed as black and white dashed boxes indicating thinning and clustering effects (top row).